

A CASE REPORT ON UNVEILING TYPE 3C DIABETES: A DIAGNOSTIC DILEMMA

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Type 3c DM is also called as pancreatogenic diabetes, is caused by damage to the pancreas. Out of every 100 diabetic patients, around 2 have type 3c diabetes, which is caused by problems in the pancreas. Cases of type 3cDM are of result of underlying chronic pancreatitis, while others are due to hemochromatosis, cystic fibrosis and so on. **case presentation:** A 34 years old male admitted to the male medical ward of general medicine in tertiary care hospital, with the chief complaints. Management of type 3c DM is challenging, requiring a tailored, multifaceted approach. **conclusion:** Proper nutrition care for individuals with type 3c DM should involve consistent dietary evaluation and monitoring to minimize the risk of complications associated with diabetes.

KEYWORDS: MODY (Maturity onset diabetes of the young), HBA1C (Glaciated hemoglobin), GLP1 (Glucose phosphate 1), CT (computed tomography), MRI (Magnetic sonography), DPP4 (Dipeptidyl Peptidase-4), PERT (Pancreatic enzyme replacement therapy) and Inj (injection).

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a group of health conditions where the level of sugar (glucose) in the blood increases. This happens because the body either: Does not make enough insulin, Does not use insulin properly or both.^[1] They are different types of diabetes mellitus, includes (a) Type 1 diabetes mellitus: The body's immune system destroys the cells that make insulin.

This causes the body to stop making insulin. LADA (latent autoimmune diabetes) - a slow type 1 diabetes in adults is also included here. (b) Type 2 diabetes mellitus: The body doesn't use insulin well or doesn't make enough. Often linked with problems like obesity, high blood pressure, and high cholesterol. (c) Other types of diabetes mellitus: Pancreatic problems: Like pancreatitis, cystitis fibrosis, or too much iron. Hormone problems: like cushing's syndrome, acromegaly. Medicines: Like steroids, some mental health drugs, or certain antiviral drugs. Genetic issues: some people inherit problems with insulin making cells (Like MODY) or how the body uses insulin. Other genetic conditions, infections, and some rare autoimmune type.^[2] (d) Type 3c DM is also called as pancreatogenic diabetes, is caused by damage to the pancreas.^[3] Type 3c diabetes involves compromised glucose hormone regulation resulting from both anatomical damage and functional loss within the pancreas, commonly linked to exocrine insufficiency. Due to injury to both beta and alpha cells of the pancreas, type 3cDM is marked by insufficient insulin and compromised glucagon release. Many of cases of type 3cDM are of result of underlying chronic pancreatitis, while others are due to hemochromatosis, cystic fibrosis, pancreatic cancer, pancreatic trauma and pancreatic surgery.^[4] Epidemiology of type 3c diabetes is about 2% of all people with diabetes have type 3c diabetes. This means out of every 100 diabetic patients, around 2 have type 3c diabetes, which is caused by problems in the pancreas.^[5] Symptoms of this disease includes Fluctuation in glucose levels, Difficulty in regulating blood sugar, Impaired nutrient absorption, Fatty stools. Some of the risk factors are Inflammation of pancreas, Genetic disorder affecting pancreatic function, Iron overload damages pancreatic tissues, Malignant tumors in pancreas. Identifying type 3c DM in type2DM remains challenging, this difficulty often arises because Type3cDM is frequently overlooked, misdiagnosed, or incorrectly labeled as type 2DM. Diagnosis of type 3c DM involves initial evaluation of HbA1c and fasting blood sugar. As per American diabetes association, the recent criteria of a fasting blood sugar levels should be >126 mg/dl or HbA1c should be greater than 6.5%. Further evaluation is required when either one of these is impaired. Some of the major and minor criteria must be present to diagnose it has type 3c DM, Major includes (a) presence of exocrine pancreatic insufficiency by monoclonal faecal elastase1 test: (b) pathological pancreas by endoscopic, ultrasound, CT or MRI scan (c) absence of related autoimmune markers of T1DM. minor criteria that may or may not be present in patients for example impairment of beta cell function, absence of insulin resistance, impairment of insulin secretion and decreased in serum concentrations of lipid soluble vitamins.^[6] First line therapy for type 3c DM includes metformin or insulin depending on the glucose levels and other

pharmacological agents are sulfonylureas, thiazolidinediones, DPP-4 inhibitors, GLP-1 analogues and alpha glycosidase inhibitors can also be used for type 3c DM. In few cases Replace deficient digestive enzyme (pancreatic enzyme), Vitamin supplementation: vitamin d, Fat soluble vitamins are also preferred.^[7]

CASE PRESENTATION

A 34 years old male admitted to the male medical ward of general medicine in tertiary care hospital, with the chief complaints of breathlessness since 1 day, abdominal pain since 1 day. Past history revealed that has a h/o of pancreas surgery (Duodenum preserving pancreatic head resection) since 12 years back and he also has a past history of type 2 diabetes mellitus since 10 years on metformin medication. On examination patient BP was 110\70mm of Hg, Pulse rate was 90bpm and SPO₂ was 98% @RA. External examination physician advised for tests like Complete blood count, Liver function test, Renal profile test, Biochemistry, Serum electrolytes, usg abdomen, Urine routine test, Urine ketone bodies, serology test for the further diagnosis.

Table 1: LABORATORY PARAMETERS.

SL. NO	TESTS	PARAMETERS	RESULTS ON ADMISSION	RESULTS DURING DISCHARGE	REFERENCE RANGE
1.	COMPLETE BLOOD COUNT	Haemoglobin	11.8	11	12.5-16gm%
		Total WBC Count	17730	8360	4000-11000 cells/cumm
		Red blood cells	5.30	4.9	4.5-5.5million/cumm
		Platelets	2.79	1.61	1.5-4.5lakh/cumm
2.	LIVER FUNCTION TESTS	Neutrophils	76	70	40-70%
		Packed cell volume	44.2	24.8	35-46%
		Lymphocytes	16	24	20-40%
		Mean platelet volume	9.4	10.0	7-11 fL
		Mean corpuscular hemoglobin	27.9	27.5	27-34 pg
		RDW-CV	13.8	14.4	11.5-14.5 %
		Albumin	3.7	3.8	3.2-5.4g/dl
Globulin	2.8	2.5	2.5-3g/dl		

		A/G ratio	1.3	1.5	1.2-1.5
		Total bilirubin	0.6	1.0	0.2-1.2mg/dl
		Total protein	6.5	6.3	5-8.3 g/dl
		Conjugated bilirubin	0.2	0.4	0.1-0.4mg/dl
		Unconjugated bilirubin	0.4	0.6	0.2-0.7mg/dl
		Aspartate transaminase	20	19	0-40 IU/L
		Alkaline phosphate	114	95	20-140U/L
3.	RENAL FUNCTION TESTS	Blood urea	15	18	15-15 mg/dl
		Serum creatinine	1.1	0.9	0.7-1.4 mg/dl
4.	SERUM ELECTROLYTES	Sodium	110	125	136-146mEq/l
		Potassium	3.2	4.1	3.48-5mEq/l
		Chloride	102	97	96-106mEq/l
5.	BIOCHEMISTRY	Random blood sugar	403	220	70-140 mg/dl
		FBS	290		<100 mg/dl
6.	URINE ROUTINE	Urine albumin	Traces	NIL	.
		Urine microscopy	2-3 pus cells	NIL	.
		Urine sugar	1%	NAD	.

- **Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate:** 16mm
- **URINE KETONE BODIES:** Absent
- **HBA1C TEST**
- **GLYCATED HAEMOGLOBIN:** 15.0
- **MEAN BLOOD GLUCOSE:** 383
- **ULTRASOUND SONOGRAPHY ABDOMEN REPORT**
- Heterogenous echotexture and calcified foci over pancreas.
- **SEROLOGY TEST**
- HIV 1 & 2 ; NON REACTIVE

- HBsAg: Negative
- HCV: Negative
- CRP (QUANTITATIVE); 89
- **PERIPHERAL SMEAR ONLY:** Normocytic Hypochromic anemia.

Table 2: TREATMENT CHART.

SL. NO	NAME OF THE MEDICATIONS	DOSE	ROUTE	FREQUENCY	DURATION
1	Inj. Insulin R	10 6ml/hr	unit/ IV	STAT/ Infusion	D1-D3
2	Inj. Ceftriaxone	1g	IV	1-0-1	D1-D3
3	Inj. Pantoprazole	40mg	IV	1-0-0	D1-D11
4	Inj. IV Fluids	3pint NS/2pintRL	IV		D1-D11
5	Inj. KCL	2amp in 1 Pint	IV	Over 4 hrs	D1-D2
6	Inj. Sodium bicarbonate	5amp in 1 pint NS	IV	Over 6 hrs	D1-D2
7	Inj. Thiamine in 100 ml NS	100mg	IV	1-1-1	D2-D10
8	Inj. PIPZO	4.5mg	IV	1-1-1	D2-D8
9	Inj. Insulin R		S/C		D4-D8
10	Inj. Insulin N		S/C		D4-D8
11	Inj. Insulin mixtard		S/C		D9-D11

The patient was treated with above medications.

Table 3: DISCHARGE MEDICATION.

SL. NO	NAME OF THE	MEDICATION DOSE	ROUTE	FREQUENCY
1	Inj. Insulin R	6-6-8	S/C	
2	T. Ceftriaxone	500mg	PO	1-0-1
3	U. Sodium bicarbonate	500mg	PO	0-1-0
4	T. Pantoprazole	40mg	PO	1-0-1
5	T. Vitamin b complex		PO	1-0-1

Suggested to review after 2 weeks.

DISCUSSION

Type 3c diabetes mellitus, a kind of diabetes that occurs as a result of damage to the pancreas, this damage can impair both exocrine (digestive enzyme production) and endocrine function (insulin production) of the pancreas. It is also called as pancreatogenic diabetes.

Beger surgery (Duodenum preserving pancreatic head resection) is one type of pancreatic surgery which is done to treat long term inflammation of the pancreas (chronic pancreatitis). This surgery is preferred when the head of the pancreas becomes swollen and painful, but this head part contains special cells that make important hormones like insulin (which lowers blood sugar) and glucagon (which raises blood sugar). Losing these cells makes it harder for the body to control blood sugar levels properly. Mainly in chronic pancreatitis patients, remaining pancreas may already be damaged from years of inflammation, which makes the problem worse. As a result, some patients develop type 3 diabetes mellitus. It is often misdiagnosed as type 2 DM due to overlapping clinical features, leading to delays in appropriate management. Neither type 1 and type 2 DM, type 3c DM involves both insulin and glucagon deficiencies, making it a unique challenge for glycemic control. Many studies show that people who have undergone beger surgery are at higher risk of developing type 3 diabetes mellitus, so it is necessary to have regular blood sugar monitoring and checkups after surgery^[8,9,10]

FLOW CHART 1: It shows how Beger surgery (type of pancreatic surgery) can lead to type 3c DM

Where as in this case, the patient complained about breathlessness and abdominal pain since one day, he has a past history of beger surgery (Duodenum preserving pancreatic head resection) 12 years back and type 2 DM since 10 years on metformin medication. Laboratory parameters (CBC, LFT, RFT, S/E) were abnormal and subsequent imaging revealed heterogenous echotexture and calcified foci over pancreas. Based on the abnormality in

laboratory parameters and abnormality in other report like usg, patient is finally diagnosed as type 3c diabetes mellitus. Management of type 3c DM is challenging, requiring a tailored, multifaceted approach. As the disease (type 2 DM) progresses, insulin therapy often becomes necessary, replacing oral hypoglycemic agents typically used in earlier stages. Nevertheless, insulin regimens require careful management due to the potential for hypoglycemia. Impaired glucagon secretion from pancreatic alpha cells increase the risk of unexpected hypoglycemic events, even when insulin doses are precisely tailored. He was treated with inj ceftriaxone to treat nosocomial infections, inj pantoprazole to treat gastric irritations, inj kcl to treat hypokalemia, inj pipzo to treat bacterial infections, inj thiamine to treat vitamin deficiency, inj sodium bicarbonate to treat hyponatremia, inj insulin R, insulin N and insulin mixtard were given to treat type 3c DM. After treatment his symptoms and laboratory parameters (mainly RBS, HBA1C) were improving.

Discharge medications were prescribed, includes insulin R, ceftriaxone, pantoprazole and sodium bicarbonate. Comprehensive nutritional support, including PERT, is vital in managing exocrine pancreatic insufficiency. Patient counselling was given and advised to visit after 2 weeks.

CONCLUSION

Above Case emphasizes the need for increased awareness and recognition of type 3c diabetes mellitus, particularly in patients with chronic pancreatitis, pancreatic surgery or other pancreatic disease. Type 3c DM is a form of diabetes that arises from disorders affecting the exocrine pancreas. Despite its clinical significance, it is often under recognised and frequently mistaken for type 2 DM. Proper nutrition care for individuals with type 3c DM should involve consistent dietary evaluation and monitoring to help manage blood sugar levels, avoid hypoglycemia, address pancreatic exocrine insufficiency, prevent malnutrition and minimize the risk of complications associated with diabetes.

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